

Analysis of excitation function for an induced reaction by nucleon on Arsenic-75 isotope using COMPLET code

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Abstract

Nucleon-induced nuclear reactions are a significant field in nuclear physics with numerous applications like as in the production of medically important radioisotopes. The primary objective of this study is to analyze the excitation function of nucleon-induced nuclear reactions on the arsenic-75 isotope across projectile energies from 10 MeV to 100 MeV using COMPLET code. The excitation functions of the seven reaction channels: $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$, $^{75}\text{As}(p, pn)^{74}\text{As}$, $^{75}\text{As}(p, p5n)^{70}\text{As}$, $^{75}\text{As}(p, p2p)^{73}\text{As}$, $^{75}\text{As}(p, n)^{75}\text{Se}$, $^{75}\text{As}(n, 2n)^{74}\text{As}$, and $^{75}\text{As}(n, p)^{75m}\text{Ge}$ were investigated, analyzed and compared with experimental data within the energies from 10 MeV to 100 MeV. The calculated excitation functions showed strong agreement with experimental data obtained from the EXFOR data base, as assessed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. Both pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear excitation functions for all nucleon-induced reaction channels displayed a strong correlation with experimental results, except for the neutron-induced reaction channel, $^{75}\text{As}(n, p)^{75m}\text{Ge}$, which exhibited a moderate correlation. Studies have indicated that the pre-equilibrium reaction mechanism primarily governs the high-energy segment of the excitation function, whereas the low-energy segment is dominated by the equilibrium reaction mechanism for both neutron and proton-induced nuclear reactions on arsenic-75. Thus, utilization of the COMPLET code and the EXFOR data base has facilitated a detailed analysis of induced nuclear reactions in producing radionuclides with diverse applications.

Keywords

Nuclear reaction, equilibrium, pre-equilibrium, excitation function, EXFOR, level density parameter, exciton number

Introduction

Nucleon-induced nuclear reactions are a significant field in nuclear physics with numerous applications and has again attracted the attention of atomic physicists to understand nuclear reaction mechanisms, the production of important radioisotopes, and other phenomena related to the nucleus (Zafar et al. 2008; Angdasaw 2013). The atomic

reaction mechanisms refer to the processes through which atomic reactions occur within an effective area called a reaction cross-section, which is the probability for a particular reaction to occur by involving the interaction of particle nuclei leading to changes in nuclear structure and composition (Nigussie 2012; Alie et al. 2019). Evaluating nucleon-induced reaction cross-sections is crucial role in advancing our understanding of nuclear processes and

their applications across various fields the investigation of different reaction channels resulting from nucleon interactions can provide valuable insights into the production of diverse radionuclides and their potential applications in various disciplines (Qaim 2001; Yeong et al. 2014).

In an induced nuclear reaction, there are three reaction mechanisms (the direct, compound, and pre-compound) reactions to be involved. In the direct nuclear reaction, the incoming projectile nucleon interacts almost instantaneously with a single nucleon or some groups of nucleons located near the surface the target nucleus. The interaction typically results in the immediate emission of a particle, occurring within a characteristic time scale of approximately ($\sim 10^{-22}$) seconds (Bertulani and Bonaccorso 2022). The compound nucleus reaction takes place when the projectile is captured by the target nucleus, in which in this reaction, the energy and momentum of the projectile are shared with the nucleons of the excited compound nucleus until a statistical equilibrium is reached with the time lag of approximately ($\sim 10^{-15}$) seconds, while, in a reaction mechanism of pre-equilibrium reaction to be occurred in the intermediate reaction between the direct and compound reaction mechanisms (Wordofa 2012).

Various reaction models have been extremely successful in describing certain classes of nuclear reaction processes like pre-equilibrium and equilibrium reaction processes with the aid of important input parameters (Huseyin and Ridvan 2013). The projectile particles that are important to use in an induced reaction are two types, the first is charged particles including (proton, deuteron, alpha particle, and heavier ions such as carbon-12) and the second includes gamma-rays and uncharged particles including neutrons. The nuclear reaction can be represented as a target nucleus X is bombarded by a particle a new nucleus Y is formed and particle b is emitted: $a + X \rightarrow Y + b$ or $X(a,b)Y$. Therefore, in this study, the projectiles are nucleons (protons and neutrons) and the target is the arsenic-75 isotope, which is a more stable isotope than the other 33 known isotopes and 10 isomers. And the emitted particles are protons, neutrons, and alpha-particles, and the residue nucleus is different according to the reactions which are called radioisotopes (Singh 2022). In recent years, there has been a great deal of interest in nuclear data on proton and neutron-induced reactions that are pertinent to nuclear reactor design. Understanding the reaction characteristics, reactor size, material type, etc. in fission and fusion nuclear reactors depends critically on the data results on the excitation functions of neutron-induced reactions with incidence neutron energies of about 14 MeV (Eyyup et al. 2023).

Every year experimental nuclear data was collected, evaluated, and disseminated through a network of nuclear data centers by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL), and National Nuclear Data Center (NNDC) (Zerkin and Pritychenko 2018) and using this data researcher were trying to develop theoretical investigations about the reaction cross-section for different reaction channels in the pro-

duction of important radioisotopes with the aid of theoretical model formulated in some programming language and computer codes such as FORTRAN (Formula Translation), ALICE, and COMPLET. FORTRAN is one of the oldest high-level programming languages, which was developed in the early 1950s and widely used in physics, engineering and numerical simulations. Many scientific codes including nuclear reaction models like ALICE and COMPLET were written in the FORTRAN programming language (Escher et al. 2012). ALICE is a nuclear reaction code has several versions and designed to simulate pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nucleus reactions, especially in medium to high energy nuclear interactions. It is commonly used for evaluating nuclear data, calculating cross-section and modeling light particle emission in nuclear reactions (Kavun 2022; Cherie and Teshagre 2023).

COMPLET is a nuclear reaction code that frequently includes both pre-equilibrium and equilibrium processes. It is typically employed in simulations and assessments of nuclear data, especially to comprehend reaction mechanisms in the low and intermediate energy levels. For pre-equilibrium plus equilibrium calculations, COMPLET is frequently referred to as a modified version of ALICE-91, a phenomenological nuclear-reaction modeling code that is especially well-suited for simulating excitation functions and emission spectra in light-ion-induced reactions (Asres et al. 2018; Degu 2024).

Excitation functions were examined utilizing parameters such as exciton number and level-density models in a recent research of pre-equilibrium effects on alpha particle induced reactions on Niobium isotope from threshold up to 100 MeV using the computer code COMPLET. This study demonstrates a strong correlation between experimental data from EXFOR libraries and COMPLET predictions (Cherie and Teshagre 2023). The accurate determination of the excitation functions for nucleon-induced reactions on arsenic-75 is crucial for both fundamental nuclear physics and applied fields such as nuclear medicine and reactor design (Morgan et al. 2021). An examining the excitation functions performed and obtained by the activation technique of an induced reaction is also important for understanding the nature of nuclear reactions (Kavun 2022).

The theoretical reaction mechanism of nucleon-induced reactions particularly proton and neutron-induced reactions on arsenic-75 isotopes remains limited, especially over intermediate projectile energies. As confirmed from previous studies no attractive investigations was done on the analysis of reaction cross-section on the arsenic-75 isotope using the computer code COMPLET within the specific energy window (Syed 2017; Taddesse 2017). Hence, based on the previous research gaps, this study aims to provide a detailed theoretical analysis of the excitation function of nucleon-induced reaction on the arsenic-75 isotope with the help of computer code COMPLET in the projectile energies from 10 MeV to 100 MeV for the seven reaction channels mentioned in the result and discussion part.

Projectile energies from 10 and 100 MeV were selected for this study because they are within the usual energy range where both equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reaction processes play significant roles. Energies below 10 MeV often involve predominantly equilibrium processes, while energies above 100 MeV introduce additional complex reaction channels such as multi-particle emissions and relativistic effects, which are beyond the scope of this work. Furthermore, reliable cross-section measurements are crucial for a number of real-world applications, such as radiation shielding, medical isotope production, and nuclear technology (Morgan et al. 2021). Therefore, studying this energy interval allows a comprehensive analysis of the excitation function while maintaining computational feasibility and physical relevance.

Methodology

In this study, the theoretical nuclear reaction cross-section of nucleon-induced reaction on arsenic-75 was calculated using computational computer code COMPLET. The primary experimental reaction cross-section with possible projectile energy data was collected from the online EXFOR (Exchange Format) database, which is the library and format for the conservation, exchange, and collection of experimental nuclear reaction data (Ozdogan 2019). All reaction channels and the theoretically investigated reaction cross-sections were compared to the information available in the online EXFOR library, which is based on standard and custom computer code COMPLET calculations (Barbaro 2021).

The computer code COMPLET is a nuclear reaction code that was developed to generate theoretical data on nuclear reactions and has been essentially developed to analyze the nuclear reaction mechanisms. It is the versatile improved version of the earlier nuclear reaction codes of ALICE-91 and is very important for measuring the theoretical reaction cross-section based on the experimental data using simulation techniques (Cherie and Rao 2013). The nucleon-induced reaction cross-section can be calculated with the aid of theoretical nuclear reaction codes, like, TALYS, EMPIRE, and COMPLET which are based on various nuclear theories.

The development of reaction cross-sections for theoretical pre-equilibrium calculations involves different nuclear reaction models like the exciton model, hybrid model, and geometry-dependent hybrid model. The equilibrium calculation also involves the help of the Weiskopf-Ewing model. Equilibrium and pre-equilibrium processes are both included in the semi-classical nuclear reaction model known as the COMPLET code. It is based on the exciton model, which uses particle-hole excitations (excitons) to describe the initial nuclear state. To model the change from pre-equilibrium to equilibrium phases, the code monitors the exciton number's evolution (Cherie and Teshagre 2023).

Researchers in this study can be determined both the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium excitation functions with the aid of this computer code COMPLET system, which is used for the analysis and forecasting of nuclear reactions. Thus, the computer code COMPLET with various input parameters such as excitation number (n_0), level density parameters ($a = A_{CN}/\kappa$), where a , is level density parameter, A_{CN} is mass of compound nucleus, κ is free constant having the values from 7 to 12), and a mean free path multiplier (MFP) was used. These parameters affect the emission probabilities, energy spectra, and angular distributions of emitted particles. The theoretical excitation functions calculated using COMPLET were then compared with experimental data for $^{75}\text{As}(n, x)$ and $^{75}\text{As}(p, x)$ reactions. The excitation functions for equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reactions were using COMPLET, following the formulations described by Mustafay (2020).

In this study, the primary experimental reaction cross-section and projectile energy data collected from EXFOR and the theoretical reaction cross-section data for equilibrium and pre-equilibrium calculated by using the computer code COMPLET were tabulated by using a spreadsheet and all the figures were fitted by using Origin 2018 software using non-linear curve fitting techniques. The theoretically calculated and experimentally obtained results of the total cross-section were compared by using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), given in equation below and having possibilities as, if, $0 < r < 0.3$, the correlation is weak and positive; if, $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$, describes a moderate and positive correlation, and if $0.7 \leq r < 1$, the correlation is strong and positive (Asres et al. 2019).

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{Ti} - \langle X_T \rangle)(X_{Ei} - \langle X_E \rangle)}{(N-1)(S_{XT})(S_{XE})}$$

where, r -is correlation coefficient and unit less, $\langle X_T \rangle$ and $\langle X_E \rangle$ are the mean theoretical and experimental total cross-sections, X_{Ti} and X_{Ei} are the theoretical and experimental total cross-sections of the i^{th} values respectively, N is the number of the theoretical and experimental data, and S_{XT} and S_{XE} are the standard deviations of the theoretical and experimental cross-sections respectively.

Result and discussion

In this work, investigating computational excitation functions for the productions of radionuclide isotopes using proton and neutron induced nuclear reactions on arsenic-75 isotope of the seven reaction channels were studied. According to Mustafa (2020), Cross section prediction with nuclear reaction codes is quite important for a better understanding of the experimental measurements. Excitation functions for nucleon mediated reactions are important for many medical applications and for the development of advanced nuclear reaction theory (Noori et al. 2018).

The experimental reaction cross-section data for nucleon-induced reaction on arsenic-75 isotopes in the projectile energy 10 MeV to 100 MeV are available in

the experimental nuclear reaction data library EXFOR (Otuka et al. 2014). The primary experimental data for the proton-induced reactions for the reaction channels of: $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$, $^{75}\text{As}(p, pn)^{74}\text{As}$, and $^{75}\text{As}(p, n)^{75}\text{Se}$ were taken from the author (Levkovski 1991). And also, $^{75}\text{As}(p, p5n)^{70}\text{As}$, and $^{75}\text{As}(p, p2p)^{73}\text{As}$ were taken from the authors (Fox et al. 2021). The experimental data for the two neutron-induced reaction channel, $^{75}\text{As}(n, 2n)^{74}\text{As}$ were taken from the authors (Raut et al. 2011) and $^{75}\text{As}(n, p)^{75m}\text{Ge}$ were taken from the author (Gueltekin et al. 2001) that were carried out in the projectile energies of 10 MeV to 100 MeV for both neutron and proton-induced reactions. The half-life, decay mode, and Q-value of the reaction data of the radioisotopes are shown in Table 1 and the theoretically calculated and experimentally found cross-section measured in millibarn (mb) are plotted against the projectile energy in (MeV) as shown in Fig. 3 to Fig. 9 and also the data are given in Table 2–9.

Various input parameters of exciton number (n_0 having values from 1 to 6), level density parameter ($a = A_{CN}/\kappa$) (where the value of constant κ runs from 7 to 12), and mean free path multiplier (MFP) of having values (0.5, 1 and 2) were used for theoretical calculations of the reaction cross-section. The theoretical cross-section for the pre-equilibrium stages ($n_0 = 2$ to 6) are taken for the comparisons of the reaction, $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$ and the theoretical and experimental excitation functions are shown in Fig. 1 in which exciton number $n_0 = 6$ is best fits with the experimental curve. Also, the level density parameter for the equilibrium stages, $a = A_{CN}/7$ to $a = A_{CN}/12$ are taken for all reactions, the theoretical cross-section of the reaction $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$ are shown in Fig. 2 and it observed that level density $a = A_{CN}/7$ gives the best fits with the experimental curve. The last important input parameter is the mean free path multiplier (MFP) 0.5, 1, and 2. MFP = 2 is best fits with the experimental curve, hence all theoretical data is done by using MFP = 2. Hence all the theoretical data are taken for all the reaction channels by comparing the six level density parameters and the six exciton numbers.

Selenium-73 Radioisotope Production (^{73}Se)

Selenium-73 occurs when a projectile-proton particle hits the target nuclei arsenic-75 and three neutrons (3n) are emitted. It has a half-life of 7.15 hours and decays by

Figure 1. Comparison of excitation function for the $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$ reaction the five exciton numbers with experimental data in projectile energies 10 to 100 MeV

Figure 2. Comparison of excitation function for the $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$ reaction the six level density parameters with experimental data in projectile energies 10 to 100 MeV.

performing electron capture plus beta plus with decay of (100%), which can have various applications in medical imaging for the treatment of cancer (Botterell et al. 1961; Ellison et al. 2016). Thus, from the reaction of $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$ the theoretical and experimental excitation functions are shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Decay Data of the Product Radioisotopes and Q-values

Reaction channel	Reaction product	Half-life	Decay mode	Q-values
$^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$	^{73}Se	7.15 h	$\square^+ + \text{E.C}$ (100%)	2.740
$^{75}\text{As}(p, pn)^{74}\text{As}$	^{74}As	17.77 d	$\square_-(34\%) + (\text{E.C} + \square^+)$ (66%)	3.9154
$^{75}\text{As}(p, p5n)^{70}\text{As}$	^{70}As	52.6 m	$\square^+ + \text{E.C}$ (100%)	6.22
$^{75}\text{As}(p, p2p)^{73}\text{As}$	^{73}As	80.3 d	E.C (100%)	0.341
$^{75}\text{As}(p, n)^{75}\text{Se}$	^{75}Se	119.779 d	E.C (100%)	0.8636
$^{75}\text{As}(n, 2n)^{74}\text{As}$	^{74}As	17.77 d	$\square_-(34\%) + (\text{E.C} + \square^+)$ (66%)	3.9154
$^{75}\text{As}(n, p)^{75m}\text{Ge}$	^{75m}Ge	82.78 m	$\square_-(100\%)$	1.1765

Source: From the above Table 1 the data for half-life and mode of decay are taken from (8th Edition of the Table of Isotopes: 1999 Update) but the value of Q is calculated by the Q- value formula.

Table 2. Experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated cross-section data for $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$ reaction

Reference	Projectile Energy (MeV)	σ (Exp.) (mb)	σ (Pre – Equ.) (mb)	σ (Equ.) (mb)
	23.1	12.4	0.5 ± 0.12	0.5 ± 0.12
	24	30	3.5 ± 0.27	3.5 ± 0.27
	24.8	65	1.7 ± 0.63	1.6 ± 0.63
	25.7	107	7.3 ± 1.00	7.1 ± 1.00
	26.6	141	50.4 ± 0.91	52.9 ± 0.88
	27.6	200	82.3 ± 1.12	86.6 ± 1.13
	28.5	235	105.9 ± 1.29	111.3 ± 1.24
	29.5	246	137.7 ± 1.08	145.2 ± 1.01
Reference	Levkovski 1991	Levkovski 1991	Present work	Present work

As shown in Fig. 3, the excitation function for the reaction $^{75}\text{As}(p,3n)^{73}\text{Se}$ was experimentally measured and theoretically calculated using different sets of input parameters and both the theoretical reaction cross-sections are in good agreement with the experimental results lies between the energy of 23.1 MeV and 26.6 MeV, but, after the energy value of 26.6 MeV to 29.5 MeV the equilibrium reaction dominates over the pre-equilibrium reaction and agrees with the experimental values up to a maximum cross-section of 145.2 mb. This observed dominance is considered an anomalous phenomenon. While the pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section reaches its maximum value of 137.7 mb. At a projectile energy of 23.1 MeV, both experimental and theoretical cross sections for equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reactions exhibit minimum values. The experimental minimum cross section is 12.4 mb, while the theoretical minimum cross sections for equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reactions are both 0.5 mb. Whereas, the maximum cross-section for experimental, equilibrium, and pre-equilibrium in the projectile energy of 29.5 MeV are 246 mb, 145.2 mb, and 137.7 mb, respectively.

However, at low and medium energies, the theoretical equilibrium cross-section agrees with the experimental results. The correlation coefficients of both the theoretically calculated results of equilibrium and pre-equilibrium with the experimental result are ($r = 0.9498$ and $r = 0.9507$) respectively. This value indicates that there is a significant large positive relationship between the theoretical with experimental results. Thus, from the above result, it clearly understood that the results calculated using COMPLET with input parameters of ($no = 6$, $k = 7$, and $MFP = 2$) are in good agreement with the experimental result generated from the EXFOR data for energy value up to 29.5 MeV.

Selenium-75 Radioisotope Production (^{75}Se)

Selenium-75 is produced when a projectile proton particle strikes a target Arsenic-75 and emits one neutron (n) particle. Selenium-75 decays by electron capture (100%) with a half-life of 119.779 days and it plays a crucial role in medical diagnostics, industrial testing, analytical calibration, research, and cancer therapy, highlighting its versatility and significance in various applications across different fields (Shore et al. 2010). The calculated excitation

Figure 3. Comparison of excitation function for the $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$ reaction with experimental data in projectile energies 23.1 to 29.5 MeV.

functions of the reaction, $^{75}\text{As}(p, n)^{75}\text{Se}$ are compared with the experimental result as shown in Table 3.

As we observed the Fig. 4, in the projectile energy range from 11.3 MeV to 15.8 MeV, both equilibrium and pre-equilibrium processes contribute significantly to the reaction. Near 11.3 MeV, the equilibrium reaction has slightly higher contributions, but as the energy increases toward 15.8 MeV, the contributions from pre-equilibrium reactions increase and become comparable to those of equilibrium reactions. This range represents a transition region where the dominance shifts gradually from equilibrium to pre-equilibrium mechanisms. Whereas in the energy ranges of 21.4 MeV to 29.5 MeV the pre-equilibrium reaction is closer to the experimentally obtained results, this is also the fact that at the relatively intermediate and high energy, the pre-equilibrium reaction occurred.

The correlation coefficient of the reaction cross-section of both equilibrium and pre-equilibrium with experimental reactions cross-section is calculated to be ($r = 0.9776$ and $r = 0.9775$) respectively, this is a strong positive correlation between theoretical and experimental results. Thus, from the above result, it clearly understood that the results calculated using computer code COMPLET with input parameters ($no = 4$, $k = 12$, and $MFP = 2$) are in good agreement with the experimental result generated from the EXFOR data for energy value up to 29.5 MeV.

Table 3. Experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated cross-section data for $^{75}\text{As}(p, n)^{75}\text{Se}$ reaction

Reference	Projectile Energy (MeV)	σ (Exp.) (mb)	σ (Pre – Equ.) (mb)	σ (Equ.) (mb)
	11.3	549	775.1 ± 2.26	773.5 ± 2.25
	12.1	501	763.7 ± 2.63	761.5 ± 2.61
	12.8	324	645.5 ± 3.22	642.3 ± 3.18
	13.8	257	491.6 ± 2.35	485.9 ± 2.29
	14.8	162	355.7 ± 1.93	347 ± 1.84
	15.8	123	244.6 ± 1.22	232.7 ± 1.10
	16.7	107	183.9 ± 0.77	171.2 ± 0.64
	17.5	85	151.6 ± 0.67	131.3 ± 0.46
	18.3	69	113.7 ± 0.45	91.14 ± 0.22
	19.3	59	83.29 ± 0.24	60.63 ± 0.02
	20.3	47	62.21 ± 0.15	39.97 ± 0.07
	21.4	44	45.56 ± 0.02	26.56 ± 0.17
	22.2	40	35.67 ± 0.04	18.72 ± 0.21
	23.1	44	27.9 ± 0.16	12.08 ± 0.32
	24	39	23.21 ± 0.16	8.66 ± 0.30
	24.8	32	19.34 ± 0.13	6.28 ± 0.26
	25.7	35	16.51 ± 0.18	4.35 ± 0.31
	26.6	28	19.1 ± 0.09	3.54 ± 0.24
	28.5	33	15.45 ± 0.18	1.78 ± 0.31
	29.5	29	13.97 ± 0.15	1.23 ± 0.28
Reference	Levkovski 1991	Levkovski 1991	Present work	Present work

Figure 4. Comparison of excitation function for the $^{75}\text{As}(p, n)^{75}\text{Se}$ reaction with experimental data in projectile energies 11.3 to 29.5 MeV.

Arsenic-74 radioisotope production (^{74}As)

Arsenic-74 is produced when a projectile proton particle strikes the target Arsenic-75 isotope and emits a single neutron (n) and proton (p) particle and also which decays by electron capture and emission of ($\beta^+ + EC$)(66%) and β^- (34%) particles with a half-life of 17.77 days. Arsenic-74 is a radioactive isotope that is one of a small number of positron emitters with a half-life suitable for medical imaging (Scobie 1957; Botterell et al. 1961). The calculated excitation functions of the reaction $^{75}\text{As}(p, pn)^{74}\text{As}$ are compared with the experimental result as shown in Table 4.

As can be seen in Fig. 5 and Table 4, both the pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear reactions are somehow closer to each other from 12.8 MeV to 15.8 MeV but after 15.8 MeV the pre-equilibrium reaction is dominant as compared with the equilibrium reaction cross-sections.

Figure 5. Comparison of excitation function for the $^{75}\text{As}(p, pn)^{74}\text{As}$ reaction with experimental data in projectile energies 12.8 to 29.5 MeV.

Above approximately 24.8 MeV, the experimental cross-section values closely follow the shape of the theoretical curve. Throughout the entire projectile energy range studied, the pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section dominates over the equilibrium reaction cross-section. The maximum cross-section peak of the pre-compound nuclear reaction was recorded at 649.9 mb at the projectile energy of 24 MeV with also the same projectile energy the maximum cross-section peak for the equilibrium reaction recorded is 691 mb. Also, the experimental maximum peak was recorded at the projectile energy of 25.7 MeV are 309 mb.

The correlation coefficient of the reaction cross-section of experimental with equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reaction cross-section is calculated to be ($r = 0.7927$ and $r = 0.7586$) respectively, these show a strong

Table 4. Experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated cross-section data for $^{75}\text{As}(p, pn)^{74}\text{As}$ reaction

Reference	Projectile Energy (MeV)	σ (Exp.) (mb)	σ (Pre – Equ.) (mb)	σ (Equ.) (mb)
	12.8	7	168.2 ± 1.61	169.9 ± 1.63
	13.8	19	316.2 ± 2.97	320.7 ± 3.01
	14.8	41	441.1 ± 4.00	449.2 ± 4.08
	15.8	72	532.7 ± 4.61	544.6 ± 4.73
	16.7	117	591.6 ± 4.76	606.3 ± 4.89
	17.5	135	443.8 ± 3.08	464 ± 3.29
	18.3	170	543.4 ± 3.73	569.2 ± 3.99
	19.3	209	581.7 ± 3.73	612.4 ± 4.03
	20.3	269	646.5 ± 3.77	678.1 ± 4.09
	21.4	275	619.2 ± 3.44	656.8 ± 3.82
	22.2	288	646.8 ± 3.58	682.2 ± 3.94
	23.1	310	649.5 ± 3.39	687.9 ± 3.78
	24	304	649.9 ± 3.46	691 ± 3.87
	24.8	302	637.2 ± 3.35	679.6 ± 3.77
	25.7	309	631.6 ± 3.23	676.3 ± 3.67
	26.6	282	548.9 ± 2.67	594.1 ± 3.12
	27.6	269	514.8 ± 2.46	552.6 ± 2.84
	28.5	251	469.8 ± 2.18	499.6 ± 2.49
	29.5	240	406.7 ± 1.67	424.8 ± 1.85
Reference	Levkovski 1991	Levkovski 1991	Present work	Present work

positive correlation between experimental and both theoretical results. Thus, the calculated Pearson's correlation coefficient is evident that theoretically calculated results obtained using computer code COMPLET with input parameters ($n = 4$, $k = 12$, and $MFP = 2$) are in good agreement with the experimental result generated from the EXFOR data for energy value up to 29.5 MeV.

Arsenic-73 Radioisotope Production (^{73}As)

Arsenic-73 is produced when a projectile proton particle strikes a target element Arsenic-75 and emits two neutrons ($2n$) and one proton (p) particles in the decay mode of by electron capture (100%) with a half-life of 80.3 days also has various applications as tracers in biochemical investigations, nuclear medicine, biomedical research, therapy, and diagnostic imaging (Ellison et al. 2016). The calculated excitation functions of the reaction, $^{75}\text{As}(p, p2p)^{73}\text{As}$ compared with the experimental result.

From Fig. 6 both the theoretical pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear reaction cross-section decreases exponentially in all energy ranges and closer to the experimental values up to 47 MeV with also at low energy equilibrium reaction cross-section dominates the pre-equilibrium reaction. Whereas the theoretical curve up to 47 MeV energy value and cross-section 253.2 mb the equilibrium reaction cross-section dominates the pre-equilibrium nuclear reaction, while from 49.5 MeV to the last 91.09 MeV the pre-equilibrium nuclear reaction dominates and agrees with experiments. The maximum and minimum cross section were recorded in the above reaction channels of the experimental cross-section the maximum and minimum are 680 mb and 174 mb with projectile energy of 38 MeV and 77.19 MeV, respectively. The theoretical reaction cross-section for equilibrium and pre-equilibrium for maximum and minimum are 605.5 mb, 0.00297 mb, and 570.9 mb, 3.29 mb with projectile energy of 36.3 MeV and 91.09 MeV.

Figure 6. Comparison of excitation function for the $^{75}\text{As}(p, p2p)^{73}\text{As}$ reaction with experimental data in projectile energies 36.3 to 91.09 MeV.

The correlation coefficient of the reaction cross-section of experimental with both the theoretical equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reaction cross-sections are calculated to be ($r = 0.9642$ and $r = 0.967$) respectively, these show a strong positive correlation between experimental and both theoretical results. Thus, from the above result, it clearly understands that the results calculated using computer code COMPLET, with input parameters ($n = 2$, $k = 12$, and $MFP = 2$) are in good agreement with the experimental result generated from the EXFOR data for energy value up to 91.09 MeV.

Arsenic-70 Radioisotope Production (^{70}As)

Arsenic-70 is produced when a projectile proton particle strikes a target element Arsenic-75 and emits five ($5n$) neutron and one proton (p) particles and decays by the modes of positron emission plus electron capture of 100% with a lifetime of 52.6 minutes. While stable arsenic iso-

Table 5. Experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated cross-section data for $^{75}\text{As}(p, p2p)^{73}\text{As}$ reaction

Reference	Projectile Energy (MeV)	σ (Exp.) (mb)	σ (Pre – Equ.) (mb)	σ (Equ.) (mb)
	36.3	600	570.9 ± 0.29	605.5 ± 0.05
	38	680	547.3 ± 1.33	584.8 ± 0.95
	41.9	587	438.9 ± 1.48	472.4 ± 1.15
	43.6	570	386.1 ± 1.84	405.9 ± 1.64
	45.4	460	313.7 ± 1.46	329.6 ± 1.30
	47	469	242.2 ± 2.27	253.2 ± 2.16
	49.5	359	178.6 ± 1.80	177.1 ± 1.82
	51.44	345	128.9 ± 2.16	123.2 ± 2.22
	52	320	106.1 ± 2.14	92.74 ± 1.37
	53.46	346	95.11 ± 2.51	85.07 ± 2.61
	55.42	282	72.12 ± 2.09	59.91 ± 2.22
	57.31	325	53.43 ± 2.72	39.87 ± 2.85
	59.93	323	43.33 ± 2.79	25.47 ± 2.98
	62.92	252	29.78 ± 2.22	13.57 ± 2.38
	67	244	19.83 ± 2.24	5.907 ± 2.38
	72.39	229	10.39 ± 2.18	1.672 ± 2.27
	77.19	174	8.431 ± 1.65	0.6651 ± 1.73
	91.09	180	3.239 ± 1.76	0.00297 ± 1.79
Reference	Fox et al. 2021	Fox et al. 2021	Present work	Present work

Table 6. Experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated cross-section data for $^{75}\text{As}(p, p5n)^{70}\text{As}$ reaction

Reference	Projectile Energy (MeV)	σ (Exp.) (mb)	σ (Pre – Equ.) (mb)	σ (Equ.) (mb)
	53.4	2.3	0 ± 0	0 ± 0
	62.92	2.3	2.22 ± 10 ⁻⁴	4.51 ± 0.02
	72.39	33.1	28.89 ± 0.04	90.81 ± 0.57
	79.19	43.7	88.27 ± 0.44	190.5 ± 1.46
	91.09	36.9	58.81 ± 0.22	105.9 ± 0.69
Reference	Fox et al. 2021	Fox et al. 2021	Present work	Present work

topes like Arsenic-70 may not have direct applications in medical imaging or diagnostics, they play a crucial role in advancing scientific knowledge, industrial processes, environmental monitoring, and analytical techniques (Emran et al. 1991).

As we see from Fig. 7, both the theoretical pre-equilibrium and equilibrium nuclear reaction cross-section starts from the bottom of the assigned projectile energy 53.4 MeV. The pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section dominates over the equilibrium reaction cross-section up to a projectile energy of approximately 68 MeV. Beyond this energy, the equilibrium reaction becomes dominant, with a noticeable increase compared to the pre-equilibrium contribution. This transition shows the changing reaction mechanisms as the projectile energy increases. At projectile energies above approximately 68 MeV, the equilibrium reaction results deviate significantly from the experimental data. In contrast, the pre-equilibrium reaction calculations remain in closer agreement with the experiment. This indicates that at higher energies, the reaction mechanism is increasingly dominated by pre-equilibrium processes. In both cases, the experimental and theoretical equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section can have maximum values at the projectile energy of 79.19 MeV with values of 43.7 mb, 190.5 mb, and 88.27 mb, respectively. Also, at the projectile energy of 53.4 MeV, the cross-section values for the experimental and theoretical equilibrium and pre-equilibrium are minimum with the values of 2.3 mb, 0 mb, and 0 mb, respectively.

Figure 7. Comparison of excitation function for the $^{75}\text{As}(p, p5n)^{70}\text{As}$ reaction with experimental data in projectile energies 53.4 to 91.09 MeV.

The equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reactions are strong and positively correlated with the experimental values of the correlation coefficient ($r = 0.9505$ and $r = 0.9212$) respectively. Therefore, from the above result, it clearly understood that the results calculated using computer code COMPLET, with input parameters ($n = 4$, $k = 8$, and $MFP = 2$) are in good agreement with the experimental result generated from the EXFOR data for energy value up to 91.09 MeV.

Arsenic-74 Radioisotope Production (⁷⁴As)

Arsenic-74 is produced when a projectile neutron particle strikes a target element Arsenic-75 and emits two neutron (2n) particles. Its mode of decay is by negatron emission of (34%) with electron capture together with positron emission of (66%) with a half-life of 17.77 days. The radioisotope of Arsenic-74 has many applications. It is primarily used in nuclear medicine for diagnostic purposes, specifically in positron emission tomography (PET) imaging (Abhijnan et al. 2023). The calculated excitation functions of the reaction, ⁷⁵As(n, 2n)⁷⁴As are compared with the experimental result as shown in Table 7.

As we see from Fig. 8, both the theoretically calculated values of the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reaction cross-section from projectile energy stars from 11.5 MeV to 14.5 MeV are increasing with experimental values. But after 14.5 MeV the experimental value decreases from reaction cross section of 969.7 mb to 918.6 mb. When we compared the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium nuclear reactions; in all energy values the equilibrium nuclear reaction dominates the pre-equilibrium one and it is an anomalous phenomenon. Both the experimental and

Figure 8. Comparison of excitation function for the ⁷⁵As(n, 2n)⁷⁴As reaction with experimental data in projectile energies 11.5 to 15 MeV.

theoretical equilibrium and pre-equilibrium cross-section values are minimal at the projectile energy of 11.5 MeV with values of 209.3 mb, 477.7 mb, and 464.9 mb, re-

spectively. But, the experimental values have a maximum cross-section of 969.7 mb at the projectile energy of 14.5 MeV and also the equilibrium cross-section is 1123 mb and the pre-equilibrium 1037 mb maximum peak is recorded at the projectile energy of 15 MeV.

The correlation coefficient of equilibrium with experiment and pre-equilibrium with experiment are (r = 0.9799 and r = 0.9832) respectively, these show both have positive and strong relations with experiments up to 14.5 MeV energy values. Therefore, from the above result, it clearly understood that the results calculated using computer code COMPLET with input parameters (no = 3, k = 12, and MFP = 2) are in good agreement with the experimental result generated from the EXFOR data for energy value up to 15 MeV.

Meta-stable Germanium-75 Radioisotope Production (^{75m}Ge)

Meta-stable Germanium-75 is produced when a projectile neutron particle strikes a target element Arsenic-75 and emits one proton particle and decays by negatron emission of (100%) within 82.78 minutes half-life. The meta-stable state of Germanium-75 can have applications in nuclear physics research, radiation detection, and material analysis by enabling various analytical and diagnostic techniques (Mirzadeh et al. 1996). The calculated excitation function of the reaction, ⁷⁵As(n, p)^{75m}Ge is compared with the experimental result as shown in Table 8.

As shown in Fig. 9, in the projectile energies from 13.6 to 13.68 MeV and from 14.72 to 14.86 MeV, both the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reaction cross-sections increases and exceed the corresponding experimental values. This overestimation may be due to limitations in the model parameters or assumptions used in the COMPLET code for these narrow energy intervals. It suggests that in these specific energy ranges, the nuclear reaction mechanisms could be more complex, and the theoretical model may requires further refinement to accurately reproduce the experimental data. Overall, the trend indicates good agreement outside thee ranges, but careful attention is needed to understand the causes of the discrepancies within these energy windows. The maximum peak was observed for the equilibrium reaction in the energy of 13.68 MeV with a cross-section of 28.86 mb. In all energy ranges the pre-equilibrium reaction dominates the other reaction mechanisms. Also, for the pre-equilibrium with the same energy maximum peak reaction cross-section was observed at 30.67 mb.

Table 7. Experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated cross-section date for ⁷⁵As(n, 2n)⁷⁴As reaction

Reference	Projectile Energy (MeV)	σ (Exp.) (mb)	σ(Pre – Equil.) (mb)	σ(Equil.) (mb)
	11.5	209.3	464.9 ± 2.55	477.7 ± 2.68
	12.5	534.6	727.4 ± 1.93	757.6 ± 2.23
	13.25	845	864.8 ± 0.19	912.3 ± 0.67
	14	896.5	971.8 ± 0.75	1036 ± 1.39
	14.5	969.7	1005 ± 0.35	1079 ± 1.09
	15	918.6	1037 ± 1.18	1123 ± 2.04
Reference	Raut et al. 2011	Raut et al. 2011	Present work	Present work

Table 8. Experimentally obtained and theoretically calculated cross-section data for $^{75}\text{As}(n, p)^{75m}\text{Ge}$ reaction

Reference	Projectile Energy (MeV)	σ (Exp.) (mb)	σ (Pre – Equ.) (mb)	σ (Equ.) (mb)
	13.6	12.7	28.19 ± 0.15	26.42 ± 0.13
	13.68	11.4	30.67 ± 0.19	28.86 ± 0.17
	14.1	11.6	20.59 ± 0.08	18.87 ± 0.07
	14.46	11.77	27.03 ± 0.15	25.06 ± 0.13
	14.72	11.84	16.43 ± 0.04	14.85 ± 2.21
	14.86	10.37	16.90 ± 0.06	15.25 ± 0.04
Reference	Gueltekin et al. 2001	Gueltekin et al. 2001	Present work	Present work

Figure 9. Comparison of excitation function for the $^{75}\text{As}(n, p)^{75m}\text{Ge}$ reaction with experimental data in projectile energies 13.6 to 14.86 MeV.

The correlation coefficient of both the theoretical equilibrium and pre-equilibrium reaction cross-section with the experimental reaction cross-section are ($r = 0.68$ and $r = 0.4655$) respectively, these show a positive moderate correlation between the experiment and theoretical results. Therefore, from the above result, it clearly understood that the results calculated using computer code COMPLET with input parameters ($n_0 = 6$, $k = 7$, and $MFP = 2$) are moderate agreement with the experimental result generated from the EXFOR data for energy value up to 14.86 MeV.

Conclusion

In this research paper, we have done extensive work to address the theoretical demonstrations in the evaluation of the reaction cross-section on the arsenic-75 isotope induced by nucleon interactions using the computer code COMPLET. The study contributes to the advancement of nuclear reaction studies by providing detailed insights into the cross-section behavior of arsenic-75 reactions. Extensive work has been done to address the theoretical low and intermediate energies of nucleon (neutron and proton) data. Thus, excitation functions for seven reactions in the proton and neutron-induced reactions on the arsenic-75 isotope system were investigated. For the investigation of the equilibrium and pre-equilibrium effects on the reactions have been investigated the obtained results have been compared with the existing experimental

values in the EXFOR database. Theoretical excitation functions are calculated by providing standard input parameters of the problem and the adjustable free parameters for both equilibrium and pre-equilibrium calculations. The theoretical and experimental results have been compared with each other by using Origin 2018 software with non-linear curve fitting techniques and also off the seven reaction channels the anomalous phenomena are observed for the reaction channels of $^{75}\text{As}(p, 3n)^{73}\text{Se}$, and $^{75}\text{As}(n, 2n)^{74}\text{As}$, which needs further investigations. Therefore, the theoretically calculated excitation functions were found to be in strong agreement and positively correlated with experimental results, except the reaction channel of $^{75}\text{As}(n, p)^{75m}\text{Ge}$, which is moderately correlated with experimental results.

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